

TO STUDY THE EFFECT OF INDUSTRIAL WASTES STEEL SLAG AND GLASS POWDER ON THE GEOTECHNICAL PROPERTIES OF CLAYEY SOIL: (A SOLUTION TO THE CLEAN & GREEN ENVIRONMENT)

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Abstract

In this research work, an approach has been made to investigate different properties of soil, such as the California bearing ratio, unconfined compressive strength, maximum dry density plasticity index, and maximum dry density by using the industrial wastes steel slags and glass powder. The steel slags and glass powder both have a great effect on various soil properties for both soil samples. For soil samples with the addition of glass powder and steel slag, the PI values were decreased from 13.7% to 10.1%, and for steel slag, they were reduced from 13.1% to 8.3%. When both were used in combination in the mentioned percentage content, they also reduced the PI, and the maximum reduction was observed at 10% GP and 20% SS, which was 1.4%. Similarly, the MDD value increased with the increase of SS & GP content; the maximum increase was recorded for 10% & 10% S.S, which were 1.92 g/cc & 1.96 g/cc, respectively. But the maximum rise was when the steel slag & glass powder were used in combination of 10% GP and 20% S.S., which was 2.21 g/cc. CBR value also increases with both steel slag & glass powder; the maximum rise was recorded for 10% & 10% S.S., which were 8.7% & 9.6%, respectively. The maximum increase was recorded when the steel slag & glass powder were used in combination of 10% G.P. and 20% S.S., which was 17.6%. This increase in percentage was about 183.8% from its original value. Hence the practice of using steel slag & glass powder in stabilization as a cost-effective solution for enhancing the soil properties of soil for the purpose of stabilization.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of soil stabilization dates back thousands of years since some soil flaws might cause delays in human activities and properties. To prevent these issues, different stabilizers are employing different techniques. A collection of several techniques to alter the mechanical or chemical characteristics of soil in order to enhance its function is known as soil improvement. According to Ingles and Metcalf (1972), the term "soil improvement" actually refers to a variety of engineering projects, such as building construction, road pavement, and airport runways, where the key focus is on strengthening the soil and lowering construction costs by using the available resources nearby. Soil improvement could be achieved by soil stabilization or modification. A collection of several techniques to alter the mechanical or chemical characteristics of soil in order to enhance its function is known as soil improvement. According to Ingles and Metcalf (1972), the term "soil improvement" actually refers to a variety of engineering projects, such as building construction, road pavement, and airport runways, where the key focus is on strengthening the soil and lowering construction costs by using the available resources nearby. The concept of soil stabilization dates back thousands of years since some soil flaws might cause delays in human activities and properties. To prevent these issues, different stabilizers are employing different techniques. A collection of several techniques to alter the mechanical or chemical characteristics of soil in order to enhance its function is known as soil improvement. According to Ingles and Metcalf (1972), the term "soil improvement" actually refers to a variety of engineering projects, such as building construction, road pavement, and airport runways, where the key focus is on strengthening the soil and lowering construction costs by using the available resources nearby. The concept of soil stabilization dates back thousands of years since some soil flaws might cause delays in human activities and properties. To prevent these issues, different stabilizers are employing different techniques.

Understanding soil stabilization plays a significant role in civil engineering projects such as building dams and laying the foundation for highways. As we can see, too much clay makes soil in its typical state

weak in strength and bearing capacity. Therefore, it is crucial to increase the soil's strength and stability, which is why many researchers advocate using readily available and reasonably priced stabilizers. According to Ogunribido (2012), the stabilizers that are available may be agricultural waste or industrial raw materials. The scholars employ agricultural and industrial raw materials to improve the geotechnical parameters of soil for a variety of civil engineering projects, such as building, road, and dam construction. Researchers are concentrating on cost-effective stabilizers to enhance the geotechnical characteristics.

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II. PROBLEM STATEMENT:

Natural catastrophes are a global issue. The only difference is the degree of change, which varies depending on where it occurs and can have very disastrous consequences for the ecosystem and the people who live there. Nowadays, it is hard to raise industrial output with the natural resources that are available, which makes it hard to increase industrial manufacturing and the rate of natural resource depletion. Environmentally harmful industrial raw materials are produced, including steel slag and glass

powder (Binici et al., 2008). These basic ingredients can be added to soil to improve its qualities and, to some extent, manage the unfavourable environmental conditions.

Fig.1: Failure of slope due to weak soil

III. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES:

The prime objectives of the research study are as under:

1. To increase the geotechnical properties of soil.
2. To make the soil stabilization economical by using low-priced stabilizers.

IV. RELATED WORKS:

- In the past, researchers have information that different stabilizers have effect on soil stabilization. One of the French engineer whose name was Henry Vidal presented the concept of stabilization in 1950. In Vidal's method of stabilization steel reinforcement were used at regular interval in order to increase the tensile strength in a material having no cohesion. The increase in soil strength, durability and to reduce the permeability were the objectives of soil stabilization.

- According to research by Canakci, Aram, and Celik (2016), adding glass powder to clayey soil can improve its qualities. This includes improvements in the maximum dry density, Atterberg's limits, and ideal moisture content. The

addition of glass powder improves the clayey soil's CBR value. Glass powder can be used to reduce clayey soil's capacity to swell. The addition of 12% glass powder to clayey soil was found to increase swelling and decrease the swell value from 5.5% to 1.65%. The hydration process improves the UCC strength of the clayey grains and glass powder when the curing period is extended from three to twenty-eight days. The addition of glass powder improves the clayey soil's CBR value. Glass powder can be used to reduce clayey soil's capacity to swell.

- According to the research conducted by Mohammad Reza et al. (2018), the addition of stabilized products to clayey soil including silt particles increases the tensile strength and UCC value. Prior to cycles, the values rise more, and during cycles, they decrease. The value of reduction decreases during Freeze Thaw Cycles (FTCs), whereas the value of ultimate compressive strength increases if the curing time is extended. Large amounts of residue are required in order to get the lowest attainable strength reduction value in the absence of curing. Adding 10% glass will improve its

properties because the reduction strength is at its lowest after 14 days of curing. Prior to cycles, the values rise more, and during cycles, they decrease. The value of reduction decreases during Freeze Thaw Cycles (FTCs), whereas the value of ultimate compressive strength increases if the curing time is extended. Large amounts of residue are required in order to get the lowest attainable strength reduction value in the absence of curing.

- The study by Gautam et al. (2018) found that the results of the tests performed indicated an improvement in the MDD value as well as an increase in workability. The UCS value increased significantly when 12% of the soil was replaced with glass, and the California bearing ratio value also increased and improved when 12% of the soil was replaced with glass. The swell index was significantly impacted by the usage of glass powder in the soil, dropping from 5.5% to 1.65%. The behaviour of the soil improved significantly after the 12% glass powder addition.

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V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

1. Soil Sample Collection:

During this research work two soil sample were collected from a pit having dimensions 3x3 ft about 8 trail pits were taken under consideration for the soil sample collection. The soil samples were brought into laboratory for further research investigation. The following diagram shows complete flowchart for the whole research work. All the tests were conducted as per ASTM Standards.

Table-1: Test with ASTM Standards

S.No	Test Name	ASTM Standards
1.	Liquid Limit Test	ASTM- D4318
2.	Plastic Limit Test	ASTM- D4318
3.	Modified Proctor Test	ASTM- D698
4.	Moisture Content Test	ASTM-D1557
5.	CBR Test	ASTM- D1883

Fig.4: Experimental Flow chart Diagram

The soil sample was dried throughout the night then passed through 3/8" sieve for the separation. These soil sample were air dried over-night in extensive container and was then separated to pass the 3/8" sieve. Then different tests were performed on the soil

sample as mentioned in the above flow chart. The sieve analysis of both soil samples collected from two different site were performed its table and graph are given below

Fig.-2: Balance with Soil Sample Fig-3 Sieve Analysis

Table 3.2 shows the results for the soil sample that was taken in order to conduct the sieve analysis test from sample 1, and Table 3.3 shows the results for sample 2. Figure 3.4 displays the gradation curve for the soil sample taken at site 1, while Figure 3.5 displays the gradation curve for soil sample 2. According to AASHTO soil classification, the soil obtained from site 1 was categorized as A-6 clayey soil components, with a 71.2% passing percentage from sieve # 200. Conversely, the soil that was gathered from site-2 was categorized as A-2-6 silty or clayey sand material, with a fineness of 20.8% according to

the #200 sieve. Site 1 soil is classified as A-4 silty after steel slag and glass powder are added. Figure 3.4 displays the gradation curve for the soil sample taken at site-1, while Figure 3.5 displays the gradation curve for soil sample 2. According to AASHTO soil classification, the soil obtained from site 1 was categorized as A-6 clayey soil components, with a 71.2% passing percentage from sieve # 200. Conversely, the soil that was gathered from site-2 was categorized as A-2-6 silty or clayey sand material, with a fineness of 20.8% according to the #200 sieve.

Table-2: Results for Sieve Analysis of soil sample-1

Sieve	Retained Weight (g)	Cumulative Retained Percentage	Cumulative Percent Finer
1/2"	-	-	100
3/8"	26	0.4	99.6
# 4	84.9	1.3	98.7
#10	940.5	14.4	85.6
#40	1306.2	20	80
#200	1880.9	28.8	71.2
Pan	6500	100	0

Figure 5: Gradation curve of soil sample -1

Table 3: Result for Soil sample-2

Sieve	Retained Weight (g)	Cumulative Retained Percentage	Cumulative Percent Finer
3"	0	0	100
2 1/2"	695	6.32	93.7
1 1/2"	1872	17.02	83
1"	3432	31.2	68.8
3/4"	4402	40.02	60
1/2"	5130	46.64	53.4
3/8"	5588	50.8	49.2
# 4	6606	60.05	39.9
#10	7381	67.1	32.9
#40	8149	74.08	25.9
#200	8717	79.25	20.8
Pan	11000	100	0

Figure 5: Gradation curve of soil sample -2

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This portion of research work focuses on the analysis of results which recorded during this research work were recorded then was tabulated as shown in table-4 and table-5 and were plotted for both the soil sample named soil sample-1 and soil sample-2 in order to attain the objectives of this research work. Work in

order to achieve the general objectives of the thesis. The results of the following geotechnical properties such as liquid limit plastic limit plasticity index maximum dry density optimum moisture content California bearing ratio have been discussed here in details with the tabulated test results given below.

Table 4: Result for Soil sample-1

Soil Sample	Addition of Stabilizers	L.L (%)	PL (%)	PI (%)	OMC (%)	MDD (g/cc)	CBR (%)	Increase in CBR (%)
S ₀	Control	30.2	17	13.7	10.21	1.81	6.2	-
S ₁	5GP	29.7	18	11.4	9.94	1.89	7.4	19.35
S ₂	10GP	28.8	19	10.1	9.11	1.92	8.7	40.32
S ₃	10SS	27.5	18	9.3	12.3	1.96	9.6	54.84
S ₄	20SS	25.2	17	8.2	15.21	2.02	9.9	59.68
S ₅	5GP,10SS	26.5	20	6.8	11.87	2.01	10.1	62.9
S ₆	5GP,20SS	17.1	14	3.3	14.9	2.1	14.7	137
S ₇	10GP,10S	23.6	18	5.1	11.01	2.05	12.5	101.6
S ₈	10GP,20SS	20.5	19	1.4	13.7	2.21	17.6	183.8

Fig.7: Effect of S.S & G.P on P.I of soil sample-1

Fig.8: Effect of S.S & G.S on OMC of soil sample-1

Fig.9: Effect of S.S & G.S on MDD of soil sample-1

Fig.10 : Effect of S.S & G.S on CBR of soil sample-1

Fig.12 : Effect of S.S & G.S on CBR Increase of soil sample-1

1. **Plasticity Index:**

According to the preceding Fig-7, the influence of steel slag and glass powder on soil sample-1, as stated in Table-4, is that the plasticity index of soil falls with these admixtures. The PI for the control soil sample was 13.7, which dropped to 11.4 at 5% glass powder and 10.1 at 10% glass powder with 0% steel slag; PI decreased to 9.3 and 8.2 at 10% and 20% steel slag, respectively; PI decreased to 6.8 at 5% GP and 10% SS content in the blend; at 5% GP and 20% SS, 10% GP and 10% S.S, and 10GP and 20% S.S bend, the PI values were recorded as 3.3, 5.1, and

of steel slag and glass powder on soil sample-1, as stated in Table-4, is that the plasticity index of soil falls with these admixtures.

1.4. This means that the soil the PI for the control soil sample was 13.7, which dropped to 11.4 at 5% glass powder and 10.1 at 10% glass powder with 0% steel slag; PI decreased to 9.3 and 8.2 at 10% and 20% steel slag, respectively; PI decreased to 6.8 at 5% GP and 10% SS content in the blend; at 5% GP and 20% SS, 10% GP and 10% S.S, and 10GP and 20% S.S bend, the PI values were recorded as 3.3, 5.1, and 1.4. According to the preceding Fig-7, the influence

Fig.16: 3mm Dia thread

Fig.17: Casagrande,s Apparatus

2. Maximum Dry Density:

From Figure-9 it can be seen that how the amount of glass powder and steel slag affected the MDD value of soil sample 1. The results of the modified proctor test demonstrated that a higher addition of both GP and SS content increased MDD.

Fig.18 Modified Proctor Test

According to Fig the MDD of control soil sample was 1.81g/cc; at 5% glass powder, it increased to 1.89g/cc; and at 10% glass powder and 0% steel slag, it increased to 1.92g/cc. The value was 1.96 g/cc with 10% steel slag and no glass powder, and 2.02 g/cc with 20% steel slag. The MDD value for the blend of 10% steel slag and 5% glass powder was 2.01 g/cc. With 20% steel slag and 5% glass powder, the value increased to 2.10g/cc. The combination of 10%GP and 10%SS produced a value of 2.0510g/cc. MDD values rose to 2.21 g/cc for 10% glass powder and 20% steel slag.

5% glass powder. Despite 20% SS and 5% GP, the number rose to 14.7. 10% or so SS Figure 4.4 illustrates the impact of steel slag and glass powder on soil sample 1. It mean that the strength of subgrade increases with the addition of steel slag and glass powder.

3. California Bearing ratio Test:

From Fig-10 and Table-4 it can be observed that the glass powder and steel slag have an impact on the CBR value. The CBR value in soil sample 1 was 6.2% for the control soil, 7.4% for the glass powder, and 8.7% for the glass powder-free soil at 10% with 0% steel slag. When steel slag was 10% and 20%, respectively, CBR rose to 9.6% and 9.9%. The CBR rose to 10.1 at a concentration of 10% steel stag and

Fig.19: CBR Machine

4. Optimum Moisture Content:

Comparably, Fig. 8 and Table 4 show that the OMC value for the control soil sample is 10.21, but that it drops to 9.94 when 5% GP is added, 9.11 when 10% GP is added, 12.3 when 20% of steel slag is added, 15.21 when 5% GP and 10% steel slags are added,

and 11.87 when 10% GP and 5% GP are added. For 5% GP 20% SS, the recorded value was 14.9; similarly, for 10% GP and 10% SS, the OMC value was 11.01; and for 10% GP and 20%SS, the value was 13.7%.

Table 5: Result for Soil sample-2

Soil Sample	Addition of Stabilizers	L.L (%)	PL (%)	PI (%)	OMC (%)	MDD (g/cc)	CBR (%)	Increase in CBR (%)
S ₀	Control	31	20	11.2	7.65	2.2	10.3	-
S ₁	5GP	30.1	19	10.8	7.1	2.21	10.9	5.8
S ₂	10GP	28.4	19	9.7	6.8	2.22	11.5	11.65
S ₃	10SS	26.3	18	8.5	9.2	2.225	11.9	15.53
S ₄	20SS	25.5	18	7.1	10.1	2.24	12.6	22.33
S ₅	5GP,10SS	25.4	20	5.5	9.01	2.23	12.5	21.35
S ₆	5GP,20SS	17.5	16	1.05	9.7	2.29	18.7	81.55
S ₇	10GP,10SS	22.6	19	3.72	8.64	2.25	15.6	51.45
S ₈	10GP,20SS	21.8	21	0.57	9.3	2.32	20.1	95.14

Fig.20: Effect of S.S & G.S on soil sample-2

Fig.21: Effect of S.S & G.S on soil sample-2

Fig.22: Effect of S.S & G.S on soil sample-2

Fig.23: Effect of S.S & G.S on soil sample-2

5. Plasticity Index:

Figure 20 and Table 5 show that the P.I. value drops when steel slag and glass powder are added to soil sample #2. The nature of the soil is changing away from plasticity. The P.I. value for soil sample 2 was noted. The PI value decreased to 10.8 upon the addition of GP. The PI values were 9.7 and 8.5 when 10% GP and 10% were applied, respectively. With

20% steel slag, 7.1 was observed. The PI dropped to 5.5 after adding 5% glass powder and 10% steel slag. When the mix had 20% SS and 5% GP, this value dropped to 1.05. The PI value was 3.72 at 10% GP and 10% SS content, and it dropped to 0.57 at 20% steel slag and 10% glass powder. When the nature of the soil is changing away from plasticity. The P.I. value for soil sample 2 was noted. The PI value

decreased to 10.8 upon the addition of GP. The PI values were 9.7 and 8.5 when 10% GP and 10% were applied, respectively.

6. Optimum Moisture Content:

The effects of glass powder and steel slag on soil sample 2 are displayed in Figure 22 and Table 5. The results showed that the optimal moisture content (OMC) rose with 10% SS and decreased with 5% and 10% glass powder. 20% SS The corresponding figures were 7.65, 7.1, 6.8, 8.5, and 9.2. 10.1% at steel slag levels of 10% and 20%. Compared to 0% glass powder, the outcomes for 5% glass powder with 10% and 20% steel slag percentage were less favourable. At 10% steel slag and 5% glass powder in the blend, the OMC rose to 9.01. When 5% GP and 20% SS were added to the mix, this value rose even higher to 9.70. The OMC value at 10% steel slag and 10% glass powder was the results showed that the optimal moisture content (OMC) rose with 10% SS and decreased with 5% and 10% glass powder. 20% SS The corresponding figures were 7.65, 7.1, 6.8, 8.5, and 9.2. 10.1% at steel slag levels of 10% and 20%.

7. Maximum Dry Density:

Figure 4.6 illustrates the impact of steel slag and glass powder content on soil sample-2. The outcomes demonstrated that MDD increases by enhancing percentage of both steel slag and glass powder content in the mix. Soil sample-2. The MDD for reference soil was 2.20g/cc which increased to 2.21g/cc at 5% glass powder and 2.22g/cc at 10% glass powder with 0% steel slag. With 0% glass powder. MDD increased to 2.225g/cc and 2.24g/cc at 10% and 20% steel slag respectively. At 5% GP and 10% SS content combined, the MDD rose to 2.23g/cc. When 20% SS and 5% GP were added to the blend composition, this number rose even further to 2.29g/cc. The MDD value was 2.25g/cc at 10% SS and 10% GP content in the mixture, and it rose to 2.32g/cc with 20% SS and 10% GP content.

6. California Bearing Ratio:

Figure 4.10 shows the impact of steel slag and glass powder on soil sample 2. The results showed that both steel slag and glass powder augmentation increased CBR for the second soil sample. For

reference soil, the CBR was 10.3%; at 5% glass powder, it rose to 10.5%; and at 10% glass powder with 0% steel slag, it rose to 11.5% with no glass powder. At 10% and 20% steel slag, CBR rose to 11.9% and 12.6%, respectively. When the combination contained 10% steel slag and 5% glass powder, the CBR rose to 12.5. In the mix combination, this value rose even more to 18.7 at 5% GP and 20% slag. 10% GP and 11 109o steel slag composition. 15.6 was the CBR value, which rose even more. The results showed that both steel slag and glass powder augmentation increased CBR. For the second soil sample. For reference soil, the CBR was 10.3%; at 5% glass powder, it rose to 10.5%; and at 10% glass powder with 0% steel slag, it rose to 11.5%.

VII. Conclusions:

The purpose of this study was to determine how steel slag and glass powder affected the geotechnical properties of soil mixtures. In this matter. Glass powder was introduced as filler after passing through filter # 200, and steel slag was added to the soil in varying amounts as aggregate with a diameter of around 12 mm. The primary findings from this research study are the following:

➤ As the amount of steel slag and glass powder increased, the plasticity index decreased because GP and SS are pozzolanic and cementitious materials. It tends to enhance the packing capacity of soil particles due to the presence of amorphous silica and other oxides. 10% GP and 20% SS had the largest PI decline.

➤ The findings showed that OMC rose at 5% glass powder percentage but fell at 10% glass powder content as steel slag level increased. This is because SS is more water-absorbing than GP, meaning it takes more water to reach MDD.

➤ With the improvement of both GP and SS, the maximum dry density rose. This is because SS and GP's cementitious and binding qualities make the soil mixture denser. At 10% GP content and 20% SS content, the largest MDD rise was seen.

➤ Because GP and SS are pozzolanic and cementitious, the California bearing ratio is increased by increasing the amount of both. It tends to enhance the packing capacity of soil particles due to the presence of amorphous silica and other

oxides. 10% GP and 20% SS content showed the largest increases in CBR.

VIII. RECOMMENDATIONS:

The substantial use of glass powder and steel slag in soil to lessen environmental issues is demonstrated by this experimental investigation. Because the maximum UCS was found at 5% GP and 20% SS addition in the soil, and because the CBR and MDD were also sufficiently increased at this ratio, the building manufacturing industry is strengthened by using 5% GP and 20% steel slag in soil mixtures as filler material and aggregates, respectively, with only minor effects on other soil properties.

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